

Status:

This virtual machine is outfitted with our entire experiment and benchmark suite, as well as the tools we compare to. All tests can be run by executing simple bash scripts located in the user directory. The virtual machine image is publicly available on Zenodo. For these reasons, we claim our artifacts meet the criteria of **reusable**, and **available**.